
Exploring Indigenous Wisdom: Architecture of the Catholic Pilgrimage Marian Grotto at Sendangsono, Kulon Progo

Anneke Clauvinia Patriajaya, Iwan Sudradjat, and Yohanes Karyadi Kusliansjah

Department of Architecture, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Katolik Parahyangan, Bandung 40141, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

The Catholic movement in Indonesia has fostered a fascinating relationship between local customs and Catholic liturgy. Pilgrimage to Marian grottoes has been a deeply valued tradition among local Catholics since the early 19th century. Catholicism's embrace and unification of diversity have shaped the architecture of Marian Grotto pilgrimage sites through the adaptation of indigenous wisdom inherent in the local context. Sendangsono in Kulon Progo is a prime example of this phenomenon. It is the oldest and most popular pilgrimage site among Javanese Catholics and other cultural groups to this day. This paper aims to explore the unification of indigenous wisdom and Catholic liturgy in the Sendangsono Marian Grotto, uncovering its latent sacred features for local Catholics. Using a qualitative-descriptive-historical method with a contextual architectural approach, this study identifies and analyzes the indigenous wisdom embedded in the spatial configuration and architectural elements of Sendangsono. The findings reveal that the spatial configurations and architectural elements—such as gates, roofs, and decorations—display visual similarities to Javanese architecture. Furthermore, the architecture of Sendangsono respects the loci by using local materials, which were sourced and constructed by the Javanese community. The research concludes that the architecture of Sendangsono integrates elements of

Catholic liturgy while remaining true to the indigenous wisdom of Javanese culture, accommodating devotional rituals to the Virgin Mary. The benefits of this paper are expected to significantly contribute to the foundational understanding that indigenous wisdom can be a collaborative approach to the design of sustainable architecture, even in sacred buildings.

Keywords: Architecture, Catholic pilgrimage, Indigenous wisdom, Marian grotto, Sendangsono

INTRODUCTION

The development of Catholicism in Indonesia has fostered a fascinating relationship between local customs and Catholic liturgy. Pilgrimages to Marian grottoes have been a highly regarded and growing tradition among Indonesian Catholics since the early 19th century. The acceptance and integration of Catholic diversity have shaped the architectural design of Marian pilgrimage sites, incorporating elements of local wisdom within the regional context.

As an introduced religion with its cultural traditions, Catholicism has remained open to local influences, leading to encounters, acceptance, and blending—commonly referred to as acculturation—across various cultural dimensions, including architecture. The Marian pilgrimage site represents a sacred space rich in Catholic liturgical meaning, harmoniously intertwined with local cultural traditions.

The architecture of Marian pilgrimage sites cannot be separated from local influences. The acculturation of local culture and Catholic liturgy has resulted in architectural compromises within these sites, ensuring that the sacred experience remains meaningful for local Catholics. Most Marian pilgrimage sites in Indonesia have emerged due to the local spiritual history. The physical elements of these pilgrimage sites encompass both natural features, such as mountains, water sources, and caves, and man-made structures, such as gates, walls, and roofs. These architectural elements serve as an *axis mundi*, bridging the interaction between the Catholic faithful

(*microcosm*) and the divine (*macrocosm*) (Eliade & Trask, 1987; Schwartz, 2014). The spatial configurations and architectural expressions of Marian pilgrimage sites reflect the dynamic interaction between local culture and Catholic liturgy. Elements such as gates, roofs, and decorative motifs exhibit visual similarities to indigenous architectural styles (Amalia et al., 2019; Leevianto & Aly, 2017).

The spread of Catholicism and the preservation of the Marian pilgrimage tradition are part of a broader cultural transformation. This empirical phenomenon represents a cultural encounter (*culture-contact*) between Catholicism and local traditions. The architecture of Marian pilgrimage sites is both influenced by and influential upon the local environment in which it is situated. This acculturation process shapes values, norms, ideas, attitudes, and behaviors, ultimately contributing to the architectural adaptation of Marian pilgrimage sites.

Local wisdom plays a crucial role in sustaining community identity and fostering successful social development. Consequently, research that explores the diversity of Indonesia's local wisdom through the architecture of Marian pilgrimage sites is essential in supporting cultural preservation.

Therefore, this paper explores the integration of Indigenous wisdom and Catholic liturgy in the oldest Marian Grotto in Indonesia, unveiling its sacred significance for local Catholics. This research contributes to the body of knowledge on Indonesian vernacular architecture and the study of architectural acculturation. It also deepens the understanding of Catholic liturgy and its influence on the development of Marian pilgrimage sites in Indonesia. The findings of this study are expected to aid in the preservation of cultural and historical heritage related to belief systems in Indonesia, particularly Catholicism.

METHODOLOGY

As an integral aspect of culture, religion embodies Indigenous knowledge that is inherently local (Sudradjat, 2019). Since pilgrimage is inherently linked to the concept of the

sacred, everything associated with it is believed to embody sacred values, as it holds spiritual significance for a particular culture. Sacred architecture serves as a medium for the pursuit of reality and the meaning of life, articulating belief systems and reflecting cultural expressions. In the context of sacred architecture, place holds profound meaning, as it establishes an environment that is conveyed through its form and spatial arrangement (Salura, 2018; Salura & Fauzy, 2012), offering an experience that conveys its inherent significance (Barrie, 1996; Rasmussen, 1964).

The object of this study is Sendangsono Marian Grotto in Kalibawang, Kulon Progo, Special Region of Yogyakarta, Indonesia (figure 1). It has long been recognized as a sacred center for the worship of Indigenous Javanese religion. Since the early 19th century, Sendangsono has held a significant devotional and spiritual role in the lives of Javanese Catholics in Central Java (Beck, 2018).

Figure 1

Location of Sendangsono Marian Grotto

This qualitative research focuses on the expression of form and spatial configuration of Sendangsono Marian Grotto. The physical elements were collected as primary data through observation, documentation (photos, sketches, notes), and interviews. Secondary data were gathered through a literature review, which involves collecting information and written materials stored in the archives of pilgrimage site administrators, including maps, articles, reports, books, and

other pertinent documents. Data analysis was conducted by mapping the data according to Indigenous Javanese using the descriptive-historical method. This led to the conclusion regarding the indigenous wisdom embedded in the spatial configuration and architectural elements of Sendangsono, which express the latent sacred features of Javanese Catholics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

History of Sendangsono Marian Grotto

Sendangsono is located along the Menoreh hills in the Kalibawang area, Kulon Progo Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta. According to history, the name Sendangsono is derived from two Javanese words: *sendang* (meaning 'spring' in English) and *sono* or *sana* (referring to a type of giant tree). In Indigenous Javanese beliefs, both springs and trees are often regarded as dwellings for nymphs and other supernatural beings. Sendangsono had become a sacred site for meditation among locals seeking to cultivate Javanese spirituality before the arrival of Catholicism.

Sendangsono marks the birth and development of the Javanese Catholics in Central Java. It is the site where the first baptism of Indigenous believers was conducted by Father Van Lith, a Roman Catholic missionary, in 1904. During the establishment of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto on December 8, 1929, Jesuit priest J. B. Prenthaler stated that Sendangsono was an expression of gratitude for the protection of the Virgin Mary during the mission in Kalibawang. Since then, Sendangsono has been planned and developed as a pilgrimage site for the Marian Grotto, serving local Catholics and other communities.

The architecture of Sendangsono Marian Grotto

As of 2024, Sendangsono has been meticulously developed as a comprehensive pilgrimage site (Figure 2), equipped with the following facilities:

1. Marian Grotto – Located in front of the Sana tree and

blessed in 1929.

2. Two Stations of the Cross:

- o The first and longer route extends from the Our Lady of Lourdes Catholic Church, 1.5 km away, to the pilgrimage site (constructed in 1958).

- o The second and shorter route is situated in the northern area of the pilgrimage site.

- o Three Chapels – The Holy Trinity, The Apostles, and Mother Mary of All Nations.

Additional Facilities – *Pendhapa*, restrooms, and other amenities.

Figure 2

Map of Sendangsono Marian Grotto

The architecture of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto has developed in several phases. Following its blessing in 1929, Sendangsono was initially developed to serve as a place of devotion by placing a Virgin Mary Statue in front of the Sana tree (figure 3a and b), marking the first phase of the pilgrimage

site's development. The stones used in the construction of the cave are white stones, which are locally sourced materials. The significant expansion of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto began in 1969 when diocesan priest and architect Y. B. Mangunwijaya became involved in its planning and design. The involvement of Father Mangunwijaya began with the design and development of the contoured land in the pilgrimage area, transforming it into terraces. After the terraced land was completed, stone retaining walls were placed, sourced from the river in front of the cave (Figure 4).

Figure 3. *Sana tree (a) a Virgin Mary statue in 1929 (b) Source archived administrative document (2024)*

In broad terms, the construction of the Sedangsono Marian Grotto adheres to the principles of Indigenous wisdom of Javanese architecture. In accordance with the spatial configuration in Javanese architecture (Budiwiyanto, 2013;

Kartono, 2005), the Sendangsono area is divided into (Figure 5):

1. *Kuncungan* is a space that functions as a terrace.
2. *Pendhapa* is a traditional Javanese pavilion used for communal purposes.
3. *Pringitan* is a semi-open configuration, with its spatial atmosphere intentionally crafted to be dimly lit, evoking a sense of mysticism.

Dalem ageng is a private space characterized by a tranquil and sacred atmosphere.

Figure 5

The spatial configuration of Javanese architecture Source (a) The spatial configuration of Sendangsono Marian Grotto (b)

The *kuncungan* area at Sendangsono, positioned at the entrance, functions as both a transitional space and a temporary resting area for pilgrims on their way to the *pendhapa*. The architectural expression of the *pendhapa* at Sendangsono is the *Kampung* structure. The *Kampung* is a still house with a wooden framework with a roof covering made of clay tiles. Both the *kuncungan* and *pendhapa* areas are designed as spaces for human interaction, intended to serve as areas for rest and dialogue (Figures 6a and b). This aligns with the Indigenous

Javanese principle of engaging in dialogue without regard for social status.

Figure 6

Kuncungan Representation at Sendangsono (a) Pendhapa at Sendangsono (b)

The architectural expression employed in the *dalem ageng* area at Sendangsono is the *Joglo* structure. The *Joglo* is a traditional Javanese architectural form, historically serving as a residence for the upper-middle-class society. This structure is characterized by its distinctive roof design, which reflects both cultural significance and functional aspects of Javanese architecture (Figure 7). In Javanese architecture, the most sacred space within the *dalem ageng* is the *senthong*. Traditionally, the *senthong* is designated as a space for *manekung* or meditation – the process of habituating the inner self to achieve stillness. Access to this space is restricted to individuals with a specific spiritual purpose or intent. The *senthong* at Sendangsono is situated within the Grotto area, adjacent to the altar for Mass (Figure 8). The Marian cave area represents the most sacred space of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto. The verdant presence of the Sana tree enhances this sanctity. In this area, Catholics, both Javanese and from other cultures, as well as individuals from different faith backgrounds, gather to pray.

Figure 7

Joglo structure Source (Kartono, 2005) (a) The architectural expression of the dalem ageng at Sendangsono exhibits a structure similar to Joglo (b)

Figure 8

Marian Cave and Altar for Mass are the Representation of Senthong

The application of Indigenous Javanese wisdom in the Sendangsono Marian Grotto is evident not only in the spatial arrangement and architectural form but also in the construction process. According to interviews and archival documents, no two decorative elements are identical (Figure 9). This is due to the fact that the creation process is entirely handmade by the local Javanese community, with the design and materials being highly dependent on the availability of local resources at the time.

Figure 9

Decorative Elements at Sendangsono Marian Grotto

CONCLUSION

The construction of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto follows the principles of Indigenous Javanese architectural wisdom in accommodating devotional rituals to the Virgin Mary. In line with the spatial configuration of Javanese architecture, the Sendangsono area is divided into four sections: *Kuncungan*, *Pendhapa*, *Pringitan*, and *Dalem Ageng*. The principles of Indigenous Javanese architectural wisdom are also evident in the architectural forms of the Sendangsono Marian Grotto. Specifically, the design incorporates the *Kampung* structure for the *Pendhapa* building and the *Joglo* structure for the altar building located in the *Dalem Ageng* area, reflecting traditional Javanese architectural typologies. The Marian cave area constitutes the most sacred space within the Sendangsono Marian Grotto. It embodies the most private aspect of Javanese architecture, known as *Senthong*. Furthermore, the entire building process was carried out manually by the local Javanese community, with the design and material selection relying heavily on the availability of local resources at the time.

REFERENCES

- Amalia, F., Santosa, I., & Adhitama, G. P. (2019). KAJIAN INKULTURASI PADA INTERIOR KARYA ARSITEKTUR MILIK HENRY MACLAINE PONT TAHUN 1918-1936 DI INDONESIA. *Jurnal Sositologi*, 18(1), 56–73. <https://doi.org/10.5614/sostek.itbj.2019.18.1.5>

- Barrie, T. (1996). *Spiritual Path, Sacred Place: Myth, Ritual, and Meaning in Architecture* (1st Edition). Shambhala.
- Beck, H. L. (2018). Back to Sendangsono. *Bijdragen Tot de Taal -, Land- En Volkenkunde / Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences of Southeast Asia*, 174(2-3), 244-263. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-17401023>
- Budiwiyanto, J. (2013). Rumah Tradisional Jawa Dalam Sudut Pandang Religi. *Ornamen*, 10(1).
- Eliade, M., & Trask, W. R. (1987). *The sacred and the profane: The nature of religion*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Kartono, J. L. (2005). KONSEP RUANG TRADISIONAL JAWA DALAM KONTEKS BUDAYA. *Dimensi Interior : Jurnal Dimensi Interior*, 3(2).
- Leevianto, J. D., & Aly, S. (2017). TEKTONIKA ARSITEKTUR RANCANGAN Y. B. MANGUNWIJAYA DI KOMPLEKS GUA MARIA SENDANGSONO. *Jurnal RISA (Riset Arsitektur)*, 01(02), 209-228.
- Rasmussen, S. E. (1964). *Experiencing Architecture* (2nd editio). MIT Press.
- Salura, P. (2018). The philosophy of architectural ordering principles. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(2.9), 52-55.
- Salura, P., & Fauzy, B. (2012). The ever-rotating aspects of function-form-meaning in architecture. *j. Basic. Appl. Sci. Res*, 2(7), 7086-7090. www.textroad.com
- Schwartz, A. (2014). Sacred Space. In *Encyclopedia of Psychology and Religion* (pp. 1579-1583). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6086-2_9001
- Sudradjat, I. (2019, January 24). Menuju Kerangka Kritis Studi Pengetahuan Pribumi Dalam Bidang Ilmu Arsitektur Dan Lingkungan Binaan Di Indonesia. *Seminar Nasional Kearifan Lokal 4*.